

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHAY****FIRST NAME: THEWODROS****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author X did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE: INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)-ACA-401D

1. Treatments, variables, participant characteristics, and setting are key components of:
 - Research problem and alternative hypothesis
 - Title and research questions¹**
 - Research questions and statement of the problem
 - Null hypothesis and research problem

2. Which one of the following elements of arguments is not a core element to support the hypothesis?

¹ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 24, 29.

- Acknowledgment and response: But what about . . . ?²**
- Claim: What do you want me to believe? What is your point?
- Reason: Why do you say that? Why should I agree?
- Evidence: How do you know? Can you back it up?
3. Select the correct source type and Chicago citation style for this source: 1. Ben Mercer, “Specters of Fascism: The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968,” *Journal of Modern History* 88, no. 1 (March 2016): 98.
- Book, reference
- Journal article, bibliography
- Journal article, full note³**
- Book, full note
4. When you have a reference list that includes two or more works written, edited, or translated by the same individual, how do you arrange the entries?
- Alphabetically by the title of the sources
- Chronologically by publication date of the sources⁴**
- Chronologically, by giving serial numbers
- Alphabetically by the name of publishers

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

³ Turabian, 153.

⁴ Turabian, 235.

5. Which one of the following compound expressions is incorrect?
- Twenty-one-year-old student
 - A 15 percent increase
 - A two-third majority⁵**
 - A three-to-five-year gap
6. It is the complete plan for executing the dissertation and is the extension of the dissertation of a pre-prospectus paper.
- Dissertation concept paper
 - Dissertation manuscript
 - Dissertation
 - Dissertation prospectus⁶**
7. All the descriptions about variables are correct except:
- We can measure qualitative research variables by an instrument with scales.⁷**
 - We can explain variables in the same order as the research questions.
 - We operationalize variables in the measures.
 - Research questions, hypotheses, and the research designs identify variables.

⁵ Turabian, 311.

⁶ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 3.

⁷ Sampson, 36.

8. Which of the following qualitative methodologies is an explanatory scheme comprising a set of concepts linked to each other in logical connectivity patterns?
- Ethnography
 - Phenomenology
 - Grounded theory**⁸
 - Narrative Inquiry
9. It is one of the data analysis validity elements that provide a rationale for how the quantitative and qualitative data analysis method fits the questions or hypotheses.
- Accuracy
 - Reliability
 - Coherency
 - Congruence**⁹
10. When we write a paper, we must not discriminate against stereotypes or demean people by using the appropriate terminology like:
- Mothers were asked to bring their children to the clinic
 - Older people, elderly patients, young people**¹⁰
 - The physically handicapped, epileptics
 - Geriatrics, the elderly, youth

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 251.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 47.

¹⁰ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, Second (Geneva: WHO Headquarter, 2013), 57.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second. Geneva: WHO Headquarter, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.